

Units of measure and styles vary from country to country. To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following style guidelines:

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).

- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).

- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.

- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg/ha N.

- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the *IRRN* Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.

- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha.

- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.

- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.

- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

- Type all contributions double-spaced. ¶

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Secondary selection in rice

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It is generally believed that further selection cannot improve the yield of varieties of self-pollinated crops such as rice that are established by single-plant selection. Even though plants might look uniform in morphological characters, physiologic and economic characters such as yield are believed to deteriorate with further selection because of such factors as progressive accumulation of spontaneous mutations in the polygenes that control yield components, expression of hidden genetic heterogeneity, natural hybridization with other uneconomic genotypes, seed mixture with low yielding varieties, accumulation of external influences that modify the genes, and retention of unsuspected genotypes within selected pure lines.

Secondary selection was followed in three high yielding varieties commonly grown in the Punjab—IR8, Jaya, and Palman 579—to check the sources of deterioration, to exploit useful mutations in the polygenes, and to improve their yields. The procedure involved selection of from 1,500 to 2,000 true-to-type single plants from transplanted crops of each variety, growing progeny of the 100 best plants, testing promising and genetically pure progeny in replicated yield trials, and multiplying the seed of the best strains to replace the old stocks.

The secondary selections of the varieties developed in the first selection cycle (1968–1974) outyielded the bulk varieties by a highly significant margin (see table). That indicates that the yield of bulk stocks might be improved by as much as 23% in IR8, 7.5% in Jaya, and 12.8% in Palman 579. Secondary selection is being continued to improve the yield potential of those and other

Performance of secondary selections of high yielding rice varieties of the Punjab, 1974 yield trials.

Secondary selection (no.)	Yield ^a (t/ha)	Increase over bulk variety (t/ha)	(%)
<i>IR8</i>			
94	7.4**	0.8	11.5
95	7.9**	1.3	19.3
99	8.2**	1.5	23.7
	6.6	—	—
<i>Jaya</i>			
98	8.05**	0.6	7.5
Bulk	7.4	—	—
<i>Palman 579</i>			
1	5.2**	0.5	11.0
93	5.0**	0.3	6.7
99	5.3**	0.6	12.8
Bulk	4.7	—	—

^a** = highly significant (0.01 level).

LSD 0.05 = 0.172 t/ha; LSD 0.01 = 0.232 t/ha

recently released varieties and to produce breeders' seed of high genetic purity that will serve as the nucleus for foundation and certified seeds to be multiplied yearly. ¶

Rice in Andaman and Nicobar Islands—problems and prospects

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Andaman and Nicobar Islands in the Bay of Bengal are the most isolated parts of the Indian Union. The total area of the two groups of islands is 8,293 sq km; the Andamans account for about 76% of the land area. The climate of the islands is tropical, with only 3 to 5°C annual variation in temperature. Annual rainfall is about 3,000 mm. Humidity is about 80% throughout the year. Rain comes from both southwest and northeast monsoons. The dry season, from January

to April, has scanty or little rainfall. Coconut is the most important crop. Rice, grown on about 14,000 ha, is second. Most rice is grown in low-lying areas with adequate rainfall, but rice is also grown as a direct-seeded upland crop.

More than 70% of the rice area is planted to the local variety C 14-8, which matures in about 200 days. C 14-8 is transplanted from July to September and harvested about December. It yields from 1.2 to 1.5 t/ha. Farmers prefer it because it offers one or two tiller cuttings which they use as green fodder for cattle. The variety is also fairly resistant to some common diseases and insects.

Over the last decade, the local Department of Agriculture has introduced some high yielding, short-duration varieties such as IR8, Jaya, and Ratna; however, these varieties have not spread as much as desired. Realizing the vast potential of the region, ICAR has established a research center for all aspects of crop, animal, and fishery sciences. Rice productivity may be increased by 5 to 6 times the present average yield. Short-duration varieties would ensure the growing of two crops per year. Preliminary trials with many of the hybrids obtained from the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project have shown that an average yield of 3 to 4 t/ha per season can easily be harvested. RPA5824, RPA 5929, IET2914, IET4097, and IET4554 yielded more than 7 t/ha in 1976 varietal trials. Because the first crop was harvested under wet conditions, seeds of many of the hybrids germinated before harvest. Incorporation of seed dormancy in early maturing varieties would be of major importance.

Basic fertilizer recommendations are not yet available for rice, so recommendations for mainland regions are usually adopted (60 kg/ha of N, P₂O₅, K₂O). Alkaline intensity varies. Fertilization experiments are in progress.

Heavy rainfall and high humidity most of the year favor weed growth. About 60% of the weeds in rice fields are monocots. Hand weeding is the best control method, but it increases production costs. Herbicide experiments

are in progress.

The first crop generally does not suffer from major rice pests, although stem borers, case worms, and hoppers are sporadically noticed. The second crop is subject to heavy infestation of *Leptocorisa varicornis*, which causes serious yield loss. Blast was serious in 1976. A large number of weevils and other insects infest the seeds of rice hybrids, reducing seed germination and storage value. The stand of seeds that do germinate is also reduced.

Preliminary observations indicated that dried neem leaves *Azadirachta indica* prevent damage of stored seed. While

fungicides and insecticides can be of value, their large-scale use would probably be a health hazard. Therefore, a study is undertaken to determine the best method of storing grains to ensure high germination and minimum storage loss.

A hybridization program using C 14-8 and some early maturing varieties has also been initiated. Large areas remain fallow because of salinity from inundation with sea water. Identification of crops that can tolerate salinity will contribute significantly to the development of rice-based cropping systems.

Sociological and professional characteristics of Asian rice breeders

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As part of an IRRI study on rice breeding programs in Asia, a survey was made of the sociological and professional characteristics of 40 rice breeders at 27 research centers in 10 Asian nations. The project was conducted in collaboration with the Agricultural Education Department, Iowa State University, USA, and was partially funded by a research grant from The Rockefeller Foundation.

The mean age of breeders was 41.9 years, ranging from 31 to 55 years. Seventy percent of the breeders were between the ages of 37 and 47. Fifty-three percent came from agricultural backgrounds (when they were growing up more than half of their family income was derived from agricultural sources). Of the latter, 95% came from families that owned their land. Fifty-five percent indicated that their families owned the land and farmed it themselves; 40% rented or sharecropped most of their land to other farmers. One respondent's family had rented land.

The mean number of years of professional experience (excluding academic work) of the rice breeders surveyed was 13.9, ranging from 2 to 33 years. Twenty-six percent had 10 years or less of experience; 28% had 20 years or more.

How rice breeders allocate their professional time among different types of work. Thirty-eight scientists at 27 experiment stations and universities in 10 Asian nations, 1975.

Eighty-five percent of the breeders indicated that they worked only with rice; 15% worked with rice and other crops, including wheat, pulses, maize, and potatoes.

To determine how scientists allocated their professional time among various activities, 38 of the breeders were asked to indicate the percentages of their time that they spent in several aspects of rice work. The mean percentages were then calculated for each activity. The breeders spent a mean percentage of 68.4% of their work time in research; 56.1% of the total time was in breeding-related activities (crossing, selecting, evaluating experimental lines, etc.) (see figure). Fifteen percent of their time went into